

INTERRELATION OF ALLERGIC DISEASES AND DIGESTIVE SYSTEM PATHOLOGIES IN EARLY CHILDHOOD AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF ENVIRONMENTAL DISADVANTAGE IN THE ARAL SEA REGION

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ABSTRACT

The ecological crisis in the Aral Sea region has led to severe environmental degradation, including air, water, and soil pollution. Exposure to toxic substances, high salinity, and dust storms negatively affects human health, particularly in vulnerable populations such as young children. In recent years, there has been a noticeable increase in the prevalence of allergic diseases and gastrointestinal disorders among children living in this region, highlighting the need to study their interrelationship.

Relevance. The ecological crisis in the Aral Sea region has led to severe environmental degradation, including air, water, and soil pollution. Exposure to toxic substances, high salinity, and dust storms negatively affects human health, particularly in vulnerable populations such as young children. In recent years, there has been a noticeable increase in the prevalence of allergic diseases and gastrointestinal disorders among children living in this region, highlighting the need to study their interrelationship.

Objective. To investigate the interrelation between allergic diseases and digestive system pathologies in early childhood under conditions of environmental disadvantage in the Aral Sea region.

Materials and Methods. The study included children aged 0–5 years living in ecologically unfavorable areas of the Aral Sea region. Clinical, anamnestic, and laboratory methods were used. The presence of allergic diseases (atopic dermatitis, food allergies, bronchial asthma) and digestive disorders (dysbiosis, гастроэнтерит, malabsorption syndrome) was assessed. Statistical analysis was performed to identify correlations between these conditions.

Results. The study revealed a high prevalence of combined allergic and gastrointestinal pathologies in early childhood. A significant proportion of children with allergic diseases also presented with digestive system dysfunctions. Environmental factors such as polluted air, contaminated water, and poor nutrition were found to contribute to both immune

dysregulation and gastrointestinal disturbances. The disruption of intestinal microbiota played a key role in the development of allergic sensitization.

Discussion. The findings suggest that environmental stressors in the Aral Sea region may act as common etiological factors contributing to both allergic and digestive system disorders. The immaturity of the immune and digestive systems in early childhood increases susceptibility to environmental influences. The gut-immune axis appears to be a crucial mechanism linking these conditions.

Conclusion. There is a strong interrelation between allergic diseases and digestive system pathologies in young children living in ecologically unfavorable conditions. Early diagnosis, комплекс yondashuv, and preventive measures aimed at improving environmental and nutritional conditions are essential to reduce morbidity

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